

Yield evaluation of F₁ hybrids in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated 29 F₁ hybrids introduced from IRRI and 60 F₁ hybrids developed at CLRRI in yield trials with 3 replications 1983-86. Single seedlings were transplanted at 22 d, at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 2- × 2.5-m plots. Fertilizer was 40-30 kg PK/ha applied as basal and 75 kg N/ha in 3 equal splits: at puddling, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Nine percent of the combinations yielded significantly higher than check varieties NN3A and NN4B. The promising F₁ hybrids had 10-33% positive heterobeltiosis and 11-22% standard heterosis (see table). □

Yield, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis of some promising F₁ hybrids identified at CLRRI, Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1986.

Year	F ₁ hybrid	Yield (t/ha)	Heterobeltiosis (%)	Standard heterosis (%)
<i>Dry season</i>				
1983-84	V20A/NN4B	6.5	33.39	16.11
	97A/NN4B	5.5	17.57	10.50
	NN4B	4.8		
	CV (%)	15.3		
	LSD (0.05)	1.1		
1984-85	IR48483A/IR36	5.8	19.91	19.91
	IR48483A/IR54	5.5	10.00	14.10
	NN3A	4.8		
	CV (%)	16.7		
	LSD (0.05)	0.4		
1985-86	IR46831A/OM90	5.3	21.31	22.27
	NN7A	4.4		
	CV (%)	13.0		
	LSD (0.05)	0.5		
<i>Wet season</i>				
1985	V20A/NN3A	6.6	26.67	26.67
	NN3A	5.2		
	CV (%)	12.7		
	LSD (0.05)	0.6		
1986	IR46831A/OM90	6.2	17.73	17.78
	NN7A	5.2		
	CV (%)	13.6		
	LSD (0.05)	0.6		

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Induction of productive semidwarf mutants of Basmati rice

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Basmati rices are prized for their good cooking quality and aroma. Basmati 370, isolated from the local germplasm, currently is cultivated predominantly in Punjab Province. The cultivar is matchless in cooking quality and aroma, but is tall and has weak straw, so that it is unable to respond to fertilizer and to withstand lodging. Hybridization involving the Dee-Geo-Woo-Gen dwarfing gene source has been tried to modify these two inherent characters.

Induced mutation could be another approach. We induced semidwarf mutants of Basmati 370 during 1980.

Healthy uniform seeds of Basmati 370 with 14% moisture content were exposed to 0, 15, 20, and 25 kR from a

Performance of semidwarf mutants and parent Basmati 370 in micro yield trial.^a Faisalabad, Pakistan, 1983-84.

Mutant or variety	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Panicle fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
Basmati 370	177.0 a	9.3 b	30.6 a	112.3 a	85.3 a	21.3 a	3.6 b
SDM18 (15 kR)	132.8 b	10.9 a	28.0 c	121.6 a	89.1 a	19.1 b	4.5 a
SDM20 (15 kR)	133.2 b	11.8 a	28.3 c	119.5 a	88.9 a	19.3 b	5.1 a
SDM22 (15 kR)	134.1 b	11.3 a	29.2 b	127.3 a	89.1 a	19.3 b	5.2 a
SDM24 (20 kR)	132.8 b	11.8 a	29.2 b	127.4 a	89.6 a	19.3 b	5.4 a
SDM25 (20 kR)	131.5 b	11.3 a	28.3 c	124.3 a	89.5 a	19.1 b	5.2 a
SDM38 (25 kR)	131.8 b	12.0 a	28.4 c	118.0 a	89.3 a	19.5 b	5.2 a

^a In a column, figures followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance by DMRT.

⁶⁰Co source (5,000 seeds/ treatment). Seedlings were transplanted 1/hill at 15- × 15-cm spacing to suppress profuse tillering. Three first-emerging panicles per plant were harvested and bulked by treatment. The M₂ was grown at 1

seedling/ hill, 20- × 20-cm spacing.

Some semidwarf mutants were selected and their breeding behavior studied during 1982-83. True-breeding mutants (gross plant size 8 m²) were tested in a micro yield trial during 1983-